

Words in English Language: A Need for Different Approach of Teaching Vocabulary

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Abstract

English is a masculine language. One of the reasons of masculinity is that it has more than 10 lakh (1 million) words and this richness is so big that almost all the sentences in English can be converted into one word substitution. The reason of such a plenty of words is that English words are in plenty of loan words. Words in English language have come from different languages. English is logical language too, except its spelling rules. They vary because the grammatical rules of spelling have taken from the concerned language from which the words came. In this article I would discuss the derivational details and the logical sequences of words, how they were made and took the modern shape and meaning. Words in any language not only change their shape (spelling) but also the meaning. The 13th century English words 'Gay' meant joyous, lighthearted (we get the word 'gay' in the Oxymoron used by Wilfred Owens in his poem The Send Off 'Down the close, darkening lanes they sang their way/ To the siding-shed And lined the train with faces grimly gay'). Flower and flour have come from same French origin, which is the etymological root is same *fleur*. The words lobster and locust have come from Latin *lucusta* which turned into the French *langouste* and Old English *lopustre*. The lobster is the locust of the sea. Inch and Ounce have both come from Latin *uncial* meaning a twelfth part, but are used for different measurements. If one can understand the etymology and philological structure of the words, it will be easier for him or her to learn more words without much effort.

Keywords: Masculine Language, Oxymoron, Etymology, Philology.

Introduction:

'Vocabulary acquisition is the largest and most important task facing the language learner.' (Swan and Walter 1984).

English language has adopted many words from other languages as loan words, later on the words have been transformed in accordance with the requirements for the English-speaking people. The main source of the English words is the Greek and Latin language. During the period of Chaucer there were three language systems in the society, Latin for court of law, French for Kings and king's men and English for ordinary people. Gradually English became the lingua franca of the British Empire, the reason behind that people embraced their native language and to avoid loss of expressions by loaned words from Greek, Latin, French, Gaelic, Welsh, Germanic, Italian, Spanish and later on when the British became empirical, many other languages contributed to increase the vocabulary like, Hebrew, Arabic Danish, Portuguese, Swedish etc. The contribution of the foreign words in English is some extent like this:-

After the fall of the Roman Empire, the fall of Byzantine at the hands of the Ottoman king the loan words especially from Greek and Latin roots started gathering in English language because of the exploration by the English people. The roots of the words are called stem. Root or stem cannot be

broken into parts. Roots or stems are the indicator of the meanings of words. In Spelling Bee competitions in USA, students are given hints on root, philological patterns of the words and students successfully tell the spellings.

Roots or stems are the words which mean a specific term and from that term other words are formed with wide range of same periphery of word meanings. For example: *bene* (Latin) = good, so other words related to the same or near meaning are formed from the stem *bene* are benevolent, beneficial, benefactor. *Circum* (Latin) = round, begets, circumference, circumstances.

In the case of words and their meanings, first the spellings of the words change and the meaning. Spellings change in various ways. And all the changes are taken place gradually and unwittingly. Influence of local dialect, accent, stress, pronunciation and vernacular etc are responsible for these changes. Let us see how grammatically these changes take place.

1. **Prothesis:** When for the sake of easy pronunciation, a vowel sound takes place at the beginning of the word this called Prothesis. From Latin>status>French>estat>Englihs>Estate.
2. **Anaptyxis:** When a vowel sound comes in between two consonants is called Anaptyxis. Example: Film becomes flim (in pronunciation) *i* comes before *l* an *m*
3. **Dissimilation:** When another sound comes in between two identical sounds to avoid monotony or repetitiveness it is called Dissimilation. The old Febyuary become February. Italian colonello>coronel>colonel.

Italian>peregrines>becomes pelegrin in French> becomes pilgrim in English.

Vowel harmony: Vowel harmony is coming of a vowel sound to make symmetry in the pronunciation for easiness. Though English has no vowel harmony as a rule of linguistics but sometimes pronunciation of some words sounds like same category. There are four types of Vowel Harmony.

Progressive and Regressive and Mutual and Reciprocal:

4. Mutual and Reciprocal progressive vowel harmony are when the frontal vowel influences the successive vowel sound. Meter>mitir, aloud > aulaud.
5. **Aphaeresis:** A change of sound in which an initial sound is lost: American>marican
6. **Syncope:** Loss of one or more sound from interior of a word: hastening>has't'ning, heaven>heav'n, ever>err.
7. **Apocope:** Loss of the final sound of a word. It means to cut off. Apocope is an elision: Barbecue > Barbie, attention>attent (Season your admiration for a while with an attent ear—Hamlet, Act1 Scene 2)
8. **Assimilation:** Assimilation in phonology is refers to a sound change where phonemes (consonants or vowel sounds) become more similar to the nearby sound: For example, handbag is pronounced as hambag due to similarity of the sounds m and b. input becomes imput for

similarity of sound n and ma. (remember these are examples of sound when pronounced and not written)

9. **Long consonant or Gemination:** Sometimes to emphasize a single consonant at the end becomes double. In English long consonant or Gemination is not used, like Arabic, in Arabic kataba = he wrote, but katabba=he dedicated.
10. Umlaut: It is used in German language, name given by Jacob Grimm. A vowel (with two diacritical mark (ö)) In English man becomes men, foot becomes feet due to umlaut.
11. Euphonic glides: Sometimes when in a word two different vowel sounds do not make a combined sound, then a consonantal sound of *y* or *w* comes. This consonantal sound is called Euphonic glides.

Principles of teaching and learning vocabulary:

Many theories are there for teaching vocabulary in language teaching. No amount of theories will be sufficient if learners feel eager to connect with the words and teaching process. Be it west or east, memory-based teaching and learning is the common platform of teaching. According to Wallace (1988), the following approaches are required:

Aim – what ought to be taught (ought, not should, a 4th standard student need not to learn word like malice or hypocrite)

Need- Need for life, daily use

Frequency- Repetition of words in life as its importance like save, help, flee, look,

Meaning- Application of word in correct way for right communication. Application of the word 'beg' in different connotation.

Learning vocabulary is not an easy process. The best way to develop vocabulary building to create environment...gossip among peer, reading newspapers, listening to radio are very effective ways. The objectives of learning a word are the following according to Harmer, 1993 and they are:-

1. Meaning
2. Usage
3. Knowing the roots
4. Formation of words from roots
5. Grammatical application

How words can be remembered: -

Grammatically teaching word is not substantial process, it requires accumulation of individual terms. Cognitive based teaching requires the following terms –

- a. Short term memory based
- b. Working memory
- c. Long term memory based

Among long term memory based the following steps play pivotal role

- i. Repetition – it harps on the hippocampus and helps secret more *pregnenolone* hormone.
- ii. Retrieval – this process brings back the memory.
- iii. Spacing – splits the memory in fragment and helps short term data to gather instead of bulk memory.
- iv. Pacing – independently helps student learning vocabulary in own pace and timing.
- v. Use – application of right word for right purpose, referent.
- vi. Cognitive depth – more thinking about the word would help learn quickly and permanently.

- vii. Personal organizing – if the words can be attributed for personally it would help the students learn, understands and remembers easily.
- viii. Imaging – Visualization of referent like an ibis . Even abstract words like heights may be visualized for better understanding with the electric pole , and for kindness.
- ix. Mnemonics – technique to remember difficult words and their meaning
- x. Motivation – motivation to speak good words for ordinary ones.
- xi. Attention – it requires understanding the perspective of learning vocabulary.

Words

Words come to us as sound and spellings. The nonnative speakers learn words by imitating the spelling and meaning. The students stuck when they grow and the number of words increases. The nonnative speakers remain clueless about the scientific yet beautiful structure of words. The adoptability and the adaptability of English as a language, makes it rich. That is why it has got the most words-entry in the dictionary. Words have come in two ways, one, words which were transformed, changed, and words which remained as it is. Words which came from other language but did not change are called loan words, like 'lathi' (stick) or 'loot.' In order to understand the science of words formation, we have to delve deep into the beautiful world of language. Words are grammatical part which conveys meanings; a word can convey multiple meaning depending upon its usage, for example, the word 'radical' it means fundamental, but radical also means extremism. Lexically words are formed from the stem. A stem can create many words. Students/people should learn to know the root instead of mugging up words. A word may have four classes, Noun, Adjective, Verb and Adverb. They change their form (spellings) which is called inflections. Look at the example:

Root-Latin			
'mal'=bad/evil			
Noun	Adjective	Verb	Adverb
Malnutrition/Malfunction	Malignant	Malign	Malevolently

Now look at the chart which can provide ample examples of the benefit of study root.

Students should be taught root so that they can learn by themselves. Chron is a Greek origin term, means time. Now several words based on the root *chron* can be learnt, like chronicle, chronological, chronology, chronic, and it is followed closely the ultimate derivatives (words formed with root and affixes) express the meanings nearing to the *chrone*. So we can break a word formation with prefix+root+suffix (prefix and suffix together are called affixes). For example: hypo (less)+thermia (temperature), here two roots have made a word -hypothermia means low temperature. From the root *therm* (heat), many words are derived like thermal, thermometer, thermodynamics. Now if a student knows the meaning of the root *logy* (to study), then he can figure out the meanings of the following words, Analogy, Anthology, Pathology, Theology, Morphology. If a student knows the meaning of these two roots, *macro* (large) and *micro* (small), then he or she may probably understand the difference between the two words: microeconomics, macroeconomics.

The way the schools teach English in Indian schools is on the basis of rote learning. It causes monotony and becomes ineffective. Vocabulary building is an essential part of language development. Schools should adopt technical ways to teach vocabulary. The best way to teach is by dint of 'root' learning. Roots are the building blocks of words. Roots in English come from either Latin

or Greek. A word can be composed of one or more than one roots. For example, the root *bio* means life and *logos* means study, therefore a study can easily can study the meaning of the word biology (study of life), biography (graph means to write). A root is the fundamental lexical unit, which define the meaning of a word according to the other affixes are added. A base word stands alone and bears a meaning. For example, *act* is a base word and can mean independently in the words like acting, actor, action, react.

How to identify the roots: Words are built either without affixes (prefix and suffix) or with them. Students can identify the affixes and separate them, the root will be visible. Look at the words.

Prefix	Root	Suffix	Word
con	struct (to build)	tion	construction
de	struct	tion	destruction
in	struct	tion	Instruction

The root *voc* means word or name. This single root can create words like advocacy, convocation, evocative, vocal, and vowel.

See how root can create several words associated with nearby meanings:

Root	Meaning	Words
Thei	God	Theology/theist/atheist
Phobia	Fear	Claustrophobia, zoophobia,
Cious	To do something	Loquacious, voracious, avaricious, pugnacious
Cide	Kill	Genocide, patricide, matricide
Pan	All	Panacea, panorama, pandemic

How to master vocabulary:

- Step 1. Select a word and define it. Consult a dictionary or online resource. Remember the meaning and try to use the words in your sentences.
- Step 2. Find out the origin of the word. The word may have originated from Greek, Latin, French etc.
- Step 3. Find the root of the word. Root words are the basics. Learn the meaning of the root, like heima= blood (Greek root) in hemorrhage
- Step 4. Find similar words with the same root like hematoma, hemoglobin.

Conclusion:

The latest report about the size of the English vocabulary says that it has one million words. This vast sea of vocabulary is intimidating. But if students can be taken to the tour of the word list, they will find that words have been derived from a basic structure called *root*. The second language learners learn vocabulary in multiple ways, and they are not instant. (Nobert Schmitt: Vocabulary in Language Teaching). Words should not be defined as a meaningful structure of letters. It will not open up the door for further learning. A native speaker of English university graduate, according to Schmitt acquires, acquires 20,000 words. Difference in definition of word will explorative for the students. In Indian schools words are taught as the meaningful combination of letter. Brdi will have no meaning, but if the letters are arranged rightly it will mean bird. But words are not only the meaning of a substance. They connect relation with the referent and the relation is not inherent but arbitrary until they are formalized by the people using the word (Drum&Konopak, 1987, p.73). The bird with a long tail which it opens up for dancing especially during a cloudy day may have meant anything like, cricket, eagle, elephant, but people termed it with peacock. Some onomatopoeic words have internal relation with the referent, hiss for snake, rumbling for wind, chirping for monkeys and birds. Words have open ended concept and does not cling to one meaning. It means a word expresses plenty of information of a referent. Look at the *semantic* feature of the word elephant.

In mind words are not stored randomly rather they are arranged as in a lexicon. The arrangements of words in mind remains in the same way as the native speakers and it changes with the number of words are added to the brain as he or she matures.

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